

EDMUND SPENSER AND HIS WORKS AS A POET

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Kurbonova Nodira Rozikovna

Associate Professor of Bukhara State University

nodiraroziqovna72@mail.com

Mustafoeva Makhfuza

MA student of Bukhara State University

mahfuza-85@mail.ru

Abstract.

Edmund Spenser is a great English poet who connected medieval and Elizabethan literature. Spenser was born in London and graduated from Pembroke College, Cambridge in 1576. In 1579 he met the English poet Sir Philip Sydney and entered the service of Robert Dudley, Earl of Leicester. Philip Sydney, who born in 1554, was a contemporary of Edmund Spenser. But Spenser's literary career is broader than that of Sydney. This happened because Sydney had to fulfill his duties as a soldier and statesman and left the world at the age of 32, in the prime of his life. However, it was Sydney who introduced Spenser to the court and hired him under the Earl of Leicester.

Key words.

renaissance, sonnet, English literature, member of the court, Earl, Bishop, Amoretti

Introduction.

Before analyzing the works of each poet, it is necessary to study his life and the period in which he lived. The poets who created sonnets mostly were courtiers, Spenser also was a nobleman. But his becoming a member of the palace has a different story. He was born in London in 1551-1554. Information about his parents is obscure but he was probably the son of John Spenser, a journeyman clothmaker and his mother is Elizabeth. Spenser became a member of the court due to his knowledge and creativity, despite the fact that he was born in a family of servants. As a child, he attended Taylor's merchant school. He then earned a bachelor's and master's degree from Pembroke College, Cambridge University. After graduation, Spenser took a job at the palace, first as secretary to prominent officials such as Sir Henry Sydney and Dr John Young (Bishop of Rochester). By 1579, Spenser had entered the court where he joined the Earl of Leicester. Like most poets who created the genre of the sonnet, he also worked in literary circles at the court. In

1579, Spenser's collection of "The Shepheardes Calendar" gave him a chance to find his place among court poets. As a result, unlike Thomas Wyatt, who was born to a noble family, Spenser was a commoner who became popular with the English court. He emerged from the lower social classes and succeeded in taking his place in the literary circles of the palace.

Main part. As for Spenser's personal life, he married Machabyas Childe in 1579. They had two children, Sylvanus and Katherine. The following year he became Private Secretary to Arthur Lord Grey of Wilton, the new Lord Member of the Irish Parliament. Spenser moved to Ireland with Lord Grey, after which he lived in Ireland for the rest of his life. By 1594, Spenser's wife had died, and in the same year he married the much younger Elizabeth Boyle, a relative of Richard Boyle, Earl of Cork, and they had a son, Peregrine. He wrote a series of Amoretti sonnets dedicated to Boyle and sang the anthem of their marriage at the Ode to Epithalamion. Spenser continued his work in Ireland. One of his most important works was «The Faerie Queene», dedicated to Queen Elizabeth I. The Queen liked the work very much, so she gave Spenser a much higher payment than other poets of his time. Spenser was not only an important statement, but also a famous poet, whom the Queen loved. In addition to the « The Faerie Queene », Spenser has written a number of other works, including sonnets. He was known for his complex language, his innovative use of poetic form and his research on complex topics such as politics, ethics and human feelings.

However, Spenser's life was not without controversy. He was involved in several political and religious conflicts during his time in Ireland and his views on Irish culture and society were criticized as racist and discriminatory. In addition, his personal life was marked by tragedy, including the death of his first wife and the loss of his two young children.

Discussions and analysis. Despite these problems, Spenser's works still have been famous and have been studied today for their literary value and historical significance. He is considered one of the greatest English poets of the Renaissance and an important figure in the development of the English literary tradition. His works have an indelible influence on English literature. His contribution to English literature is enormous. In particular, the epic of Spenser « The Faerie Queene » is one of the most important works of English literature. It tells the story of knights seeking to conquer evil and uphold virtue, and is filled with detailed descriptions of allegorical figures, characters, and landscapes. There are further innovations in language and style, which means that Spenser's use of the language was very innovative, and he introduced many new words and phrases into English. He is

also known for his refined and elegant style of writing, which emphasizes complex images, references to classical literature, and the musicality of the language. He also explores political and religious themes: Spenser's work often touches upon political and religious themes, and he was known for his support of Queen Elizabeth I and the Protestant Reformation. He also wrote extensively on the complexities of human nature and the struggle between good and evil. And finally, Spenser has a place in the development of the English sonnet. He helped to develop the English form of the sonnet, a new and innovative poetic form of XVI th century. He experimented with the form of the sonnet, creating his own unique rhyme scheme and structure, which influenced later poets such as William Shakespeare. Speaking about his work in sonnet genre, it is worth mentioning a series of sonnets "Amoretti". This sequence of sonnets was written by Spenser for his second wife, Elizabeth Boyle. In sonnet 74, Spenser says that there are three Elizabeths in his life who have shown him mercy: his mother, his queen, and his wife.

Results. Spenser wrote "Amoretti" to celebrate his meeting with Elizabeth Boyle and celebrate their wedding. Therefore, the sonnets in «Amoretti» are also considered a small gift for Elizabeth Boyle. For this reason literary scholars call these sonnets «Amoretti». It is known that Amoretti was written following the Renaissance views that were so popular in the 1580s. In sonnets Spenser follows the sonnet tradition of Petrarch. However, there is a difference between the content of «Amoretti» and sonnets of Petrarch and Wyatt. In «Amoretti» Spenser wrote about marriage and , and in sonnets Petrarch and Wyatt tells about unrequited love and unfulfilled desires. Spenser's «Amoretti» begins with the tension between the pursuit of love, the physical and spiritual aspects of love, but gradually turns into a journey of mutual love, culminating in marriage.

To emphasize marriage as a necessary consequence of love, Spenser wrote the wedding song "Epithalamion", dedicated to his marriage to Elizabeth Boyle. Amoretti cannot be studied separately from "Epithalamion". According to Spenser, love in Amoretti should be legalized and celebrated in marriage. Thus, "Amoretti" and "Epithalamion" are two separate parts of a single whole that should be studied together. In "Epithalamion", Spenser suggests that the anxieties of love can only be resolved through a Christian marriage. "Amoretti" and "Epithalamion" also have a religious ritual aspect. In the introduction to Edmund Spenser's book «Amoretti and Epithalamion: A Critical Edition» Larsen dwells on the nature of religious rituals. Each of the 89 sonnets is reported to have consecutive dates between 1594 and the wedding day. "...beginning on Wednesday 23 January 1594 and running, with one interval, through to Friday 17 May 1594: they correspond with the daily

and sequential order of scriptural readings that are prescribed for those dates by the liturgical calendar of the Church of England. Their conceits, themes, ideas, imagery, words, and sometimes their rhetorical structure consistently and successively match like particulars in these daily readings. Consequently the final structure of Amoretti and Epithalamion has been shaped by Spenser as a liturgico-poetic artifact." [Larsen 3]. Amoretti is thus associated with the yearly liturgical period of the Church. It is not a mistake to say that they are also linked to the end of the natural season. This work also has the influence of Petrarch. However, according to Larsen, the events in the work and Petrarch's influence on the author paradoxically emphasize Amoretti's Old English nature. Although Spenser relied heavily on the themes and typical structures of Petrarch, it is difficult to identify any specific sources in Petrarch's work. The references are very short. Furthermore, as it was mentioned above, the theme of unrequited love is being replaced by the legalization of love through the covenant of marriage, which is typical to Protestants and Englishmen.

In terms of "Amoretti", it is composed of 89 sonnets. Literary scholars say that Amoretti and Epithalamion consist of three parts. The first section, Amoretti 1-57, continues until Holy Week and corresponds to the seasons of Hilary and Lent (Hilary's season begins on January 11, and Holy Week, the week before Easter, often falls in early April). These early sonnets depict intimacy and personal problems between lovers by direct praise. So we can enjoy the gentle moments between the groom and his lover, the polite compliment of his lover. By reference to biblical sources, the manner of courting the mistress has been expanded and endowed with spiritual meaning, thereby elevating the relationship between man and woman over the ordinary. The influence of Petrarch is evident in the first act, when the lover attempts to court his lover. However, in addition to imitating Petrarch, Spenser also parodies Petrarch's poetry lines in the first part. As the sonnets develop, it becomes clear that Spenser considers Petrarch's ideas insufficient to convey a love relationship. Since Petrarch's sonnets mostly depict unrequited love, this scheme did not fit the depiction of relationships in Spenser's sonnets. There is mutual care between the sonnets of Petrarch and Wyatt. The relationship between lovers is unimaginable, that is, impossible. Spenser manages the tension created by the love affair in Petrarch's stories, creating a new language that gives space for interaction and physical intimacy, and he finds this language in religion. Because of this, as sonnets develop, Spenser's voice becomes more serious and spiritual.

The second part coincides with Holy Week and the Low Sunday preceding the Easter season. Amoretti consists of sonnets 58 - 75. Low Sunday is the Sunday after the Resurrection of Jesus Christ. These sonnets are considered a turning point in Amoretti. From the parody of the first part, he goes on to the tone of reflection and awe, which is replaced by the English Protestant resolution of the sonnet. They make love and relationships part of their divine image.

The third section consists of sonnets, which Spenser initially did not intend to write, and which do not match specific dates in the calendar. They are described as anticipation sonnets. They are like a bridge between the joyous public celebration of Epithalamion and the tension of the previous parts leading up to resolutions.

Conclusion. So, Edmund Spenser's literary career had a significant impact on the development of English literature. His works demonstrate his mastery of poetry, his exploration of complex themes, and his ability to combine political and religious ideas with his writings. Spenser's influence can be seen in subsequent poets and writers, and his works continue to be studied and celebrated for their poetic beauty and depth of meaning.

Amoretti is regarded as one of the finest collections of sonnets in the English language. It showcases Spenser's skill as a poet and his ability to capture the nuances of love and courtship. The sequence is characterized by its lyrical beauty, emotional depth, and intricate use of poetic devices. It remains an important contribution to the tradition of sonnet sequences and is regarded as one of the finest collections of sonnets in English literature.

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